

Influence of Self-Awareness on Pre-Marital Sexuality of In-School Female Adolescent Students in Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The study the influence of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of the study, one research question and hypothesis was posed. The study adopted the survey research design, with a population of eleven thousand and two (11, 002) female adolescents the aged 16-21 years. The sample comprised 850 in-school female adolescents drawn from 11 public and private secondary schools in the Local Government Area. A questionnaire developed by the researcher titled "In-school Female Adolescent Students Opinion Questionnaire (IFASOQ)" was used for data collection. The data gathered were analyzed with One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The found that self-awareness has a significant influence on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents (with the following dimensions: intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity and overall). It was recommended among others that adolescents should be given full orientation on how to study, know and understand themselves and take correct decisions promptly, because self-awareness enables one to be more realistic when taking decision. They should be taught how to regulate and be in full control of their emotions, as well as to understand that though it is good to be empathetic, it should be done with reservation especially when it has to do with the opposite sex. (Word counts= 217).

Keyword: Self-awareness, pre-marital sex, in-school female, adolescents, intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity.

Introduction

Pre-marital sex also known as non-marital sex, youthful sex or adolescent sex refers to the engagement in sexual intercourse by individuals of opposite sex who are not yet married to each other, but who may or may not eventually marry each other (Anene, Ojinaka & Nche, 2017). Basically, every society has what it upholds as values regarding sexuality and what constitutes premarital sex. Some decades ago in Nigeria which Cross River State is part of, the problem of pre-marital sex was not really rampant, principally because, it was a taboo to talk about sex openly, talkless of engaging in pre-marital sex to lose virginity before actual marriage.

More so, societal norms prohibited male and female members of the society from having any form of physical contact or even to approach a member of the opposite sex to express a noble course such as the desire to marry. As was noted by Abdullah (2013), where there was need for marriage the bridegroom was not expected to approach the bride to be, but the family of the would be bridegroom would approach the family of the would be bride to solicit for their daughters hand in marriage to their son (Ayaji, 2002). Sexual provocation such as wearing provocative dresses and touching an individuals' body part was prohibited. Moral values were upheld and this reflected in the dressing and behaviour of both the male and female members of the society. When a few deviated and entered into a relationship that involved sex, this was done secretly. In fact, the word

sex was sacred and was treated and is still treated in some Nigerian society as a secret that should not be opened where young people are (Ajia, 2004, Nwosu; 2006; & Ukechi, 2007).

In our schools today, the problem of sexuality is becoming more and more worrisome. Age long tradition of self honour and upholding moral values especially as it relates to sexual behaviours has almost completely been lost. Today in our schools it is observed that adolescents are indulging more and more in unacceptable sexual behaviour. Female adolescents who are supposed to pay attention to their studies are rather indulging in premarital sexual behaviour and permissiveness diverting their attention from their academic work. They devote interest to watching pornographic pictures, wearing revealing dresses, some take up a dress code which is not approved by the school such as cutting their skirts to be unnecessarily shorter than the approved length by the school to what is popularly known as mini- skirts, short gowns. They indulge in night calls to boyfriends, kissing and romancing in the public, sending text messages to their boyfriends even while the teacher is teaching in the classroom, they exchange love notes, divert the money given to them by their parents for academic work to buying things for their boyfriends to make them happy and for buying of make-up kits to make themselves attractive to the opposite sex. They prefer attending parties of all kinds, stay in quite corners of the schools, some even touch the private parts of the opposite sex openly and without shame. Some do not return back home from school on time but rather prefer to loiter around with friends, while some spend their time indulging in conversations concerning their relationships which hinders interest and concentration for academic excellence. Some adolescents develop truant behaviours, they go to school early but escape to their boyfriends houses to stay especially if their boyfriends are not in the same school with them or older than them, they become insolent to both their parents and teachers alike, they do not have regards for rules and regulations at home, school and the larger society as long as they satisfy themselves and their friends. They no longer have regards for their seniors and become very arrogant, they actually indulge in risky sexual behaviour including unprotected sexual intercourse, multiple sex partners and to some outright prostitution.

Though some people may look at indulging in sex as having economic and social benefits, at the end it brings about bitter consequences. The consequences of in-school adolescent engagement in premarital sexuality are enormous. Some of these consequences have long term and life threatening effect on in-school female adolescent students health as well as their academic social and economic lives. As a result of the in-school female students promiscuity, some of them may get pregnant and dropout of school, and sometimes attempt abortion and end up damaging their reproductive organ which could lead to cases of infertility and loss of lives. Other problems that may arise from the above mentioned issues is pre-mature motherhood, low education with it attendant economic hardship (Krukru, 2016). Loss of self-respect, living in bondage, feeling of regret, depression, feeling of guilt, fear of future commitment, loss of family/parents support, and corruption of character (Uno, 2006; Umar, 2013).

There is no gain saying, pre-marital sex among in-school female adolescent work contrary to the achievement of the school goals, and learning outcome. It affects the teaching and learning process, militates against the effective performance of teachers, jeopardizes the administration of the school and grossly limits the progress of the learners. Therefore considering the problems which pre-marital sex possess in schools, educational stakeholders have made several attempt to curb these problems, school administrators prescribe codes of conduct for schools, put in place certain disciplinary measures that deals with pre-marital sex, such as boys should not be seen standing or sitting with girls in dark or private corners in schools, they should not be seen loitering around the school compound before, during and after school period, they should not be found in hidden places in the school, nor using of android phones, no answering of phone calls in the school, no wearing of uniform that does not conform with the schools prescribed rules and regulations, suspension or expulsion of any girl who is pregnant while in school and relating such information to their parents. Government, through the Federal Health Management Board in (2009) had created awareness and carried out series of campaigns on the

social media to create public awareness on the danger and circulation of sexually transmitted diseases such as Human Immune Virus (HIV), Acquire Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) and other Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) contracted as a result of indulging in pre-marital sex. Non-governmental Organization (NGO) such as Girls Power Initiative (GPI) in Cross River State also create awareness. Girls Power initiative do address challenges facing girls and do equip them with information, skills and opportunities to enable them grow into self-actualizing young women (Ubi, Effiom & Esuabana, 2021). Equally researchers have conducted researches on this area to see how this problem can be resolved. Parents are not left out in putting corrective measures to the attitude of in-school female adolescents towards pre-marital sexuality. They frown, warn, stop paying of school fees out of anger. In some families, parents at times decide to forgive their in-school female adolescents who had fallen victim of unwanted pregnancies and take the babies from them and return them back to school but sometimes these girls do not refrain from having sexual partners that get them pregnant again. This weak attitude of some in-school female adolescents students towards pre-marital sexuality is what poses concern to the researcher thus to look at the influence of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescent students in secondary schools.

Statement of the problem

The issue of pre-marital sexuality among adolescence female has been the subject of concern to all and sundry in the society. This study is necessitated by the increasing rate of premarital sexuality among female adolescence in secondary schools. It is disheartening as noted earlier that in-school female adolescent students are distracted from serious academic pursuit due to their indulgence in pre-marital sexual activities while in school. This has resulted in a damaging effect in the life of in-school female adolescent students. School administrators have put in place disciplinary measures ranging from suspension, cutting of grasses, corporal punishment and outright expulsion in their attempt to curb the menace but to no avail. Most counselors have been guiding these students, and emphasis has been laid on the importance of education and why they should not indulge in premarital sex. Government has legislated against adolescent pre-marital sexual behaviour and has created awareness as to the consequences of pre-marital sex. Non- Governmental Organizations (NGO) like Girls Power Initiative (GPI), State Action Committee on AIDS (SACA) have carried out massive campaign against casual sex and the prevalence of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS), all in attempt to discourage adolescent girls from indulging in premarital sex. The psychologist has intervened at the individual and system levels, and develops, implement and evaluate programmes to promote positive learning environments for children and youth from diverse background. The researcher has carried out a lot of researches concerning premarital sex and how to curb it, parents have not relented in their efforts to correct and protect their children from this deviant behaviour, yet this problem still persists. It is this that has made the researcher curious in finding out the influence of self-awareness on influence pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in secondary schools in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescence in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research questions

How does self-awareness influence pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in terms of intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity.

Statement of hypotheses

Self-awareness has no significant influence on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in terms of intimacy, romance, and sexual promiscuity

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theoretical framework

The study relies on the psychoanalytic theory of personality. The psychoanalytic theory of personality was propounded by Sigmund Freud. The theory states that man is a dynamic system of energies comprising the “**Id**”, the “**ego**” and the “**superego**” representing biological, the psychological and the social forces respectively.

“**Id**” is said to be the primary aspect of personality. Freud said, it is the energy system coming from birth which energizes man throughout life. It is impulsive, raw and uncontrolled desire. The ‘**Id**’ is characteristically controlled by the pleasure principle. Once activated it demands immediate gratification. It is always seeking to derive pleasure from the environment by all means without minding the consequences. The ‘**Id**’ is concerned with avoiding pains. It cannot tolerate tension, it seeks immediate gratification without regards to realities of life or morals of any type. The ‘**Id**’ follows no morality, no fear and no discipline.

The ‘**ego**’ is said to be that part of “**Id**” which has been modified by its proximity to the external world and the influences the external world has on it. It does not exist at birth but is a product of individual’s conscious awareness. The “**ego**” tries to suppress the innate desires of ‘**Id**’ in accordance with the demands of the environment. The ego has veto power with regards to the determination of behaviour and controls the irrational and immoral demands of the ‘**Id**’.

The “**superego**” is the third subdivision of personality representing social force. It is a function of the individual’s early socialization process. It is the product of a child’s upbringing through parental restrictions and prohibitions as well as admonition and reinforcement by siblings, teachers, peers, and other significant figures. All the customs, norms and values to which the child is exposed to becomes internalized as a voice of conscience and forms the child’s lifestyle.

The implication of this theory to this work is that it will help to identify what motivates the adolescent female students’ sexual orientation and also find out their level of morality. It will help in counseling the students according to whatever results this research will produce. This theory will be very useful in developing positive emotions and emotional intelligence among in-school female adolescents.

Also, Kohlbergs Theory of Moral Development of 1963 forms the basis of this study. Lawrence Kohlberg a psychologist in his study of moral development in children intended to know whether there are universal stages in the development of morals. Using Piaget’s work on moral judgment of the child as the background, he presented series of stories depicting moral dilemma to children and adult of various ages and background. He identified three levels of moral development each containing two stages which make up a total of six stages, there are Preconventional, conventional, and post conventional levels.

The premise of the theory is that people move through these stage in a fixed order, and that moral understanding is linked to cognitive development and the cognitive developmentalist believes that morality is the ethical principles used by an individual to judge his or her own behaviour and the behaviour of others which teaches the adolescents the importance of emotional intelligence. Below are the explanation of the different level and stages of Kohlberg’s theory of moral development:

Per-conventional level, conventional level and post-conventional level of moral reasoning

Level one; Pre-conventional level of moral reasoning (ages one and two

Stage 1: Obedience and punishment orientation

This is the stage of obedience and punishment orientation. At this stage, morality is mostly determined by the power of authority figures. The child at this age yields absolutely to the will, view and demands in order to avoid punishment.

Stage 2: Self-interest orientation

The child is still egocentric. The child conforms so as to get a reward in exchange. The principle of give and take operates here.

Conventional level: (ages three and four)

Stage 3: Interpersonal accord and conformity (the good boy, good girl attitude)

This levels centers on rules and expectations of others and this form, the major determinant of right and wrong.

Stage 4: Authority and social-order maintaining orientation

During this stage, right implies doing one's duties in the society, and upholding the social orders. A desire for social approval no longer determine moral judgment

Post-conventional level: (ages eleven and above)

Stage 5: Social contract orientation

In this stage right actions tend to be defined with the following dimensions: the standards, requirements and rights in society as agreed upon. Laws are seen as necessary to preserve the social order and ensure basic right of life and liberty. It is also believed at this stage that in the enforcement of the accepted set of reasoning, the fundamental human rights of every member of the society has to be respected regardless of difference belief, race or social class.

Stage 6: Universal ethical principle (principled conscience)

This stage view ethical principles as being self-chosen and based on abstract concepts such as justice and the value of human right in making choices, the individual not only considers the rules of the society, but also the extent to which universal ethical principles apply.

The implication of this theory to this research bothers on the second level of Kohlberg's theory which is the conventional level. Children in conventional level consider their feelings and that of others in making decisions. It is also known that the adolescence period is a time when individuals learn a lot on their peer group for social and emotional support. If the peer group is an immoral one, then female adolescents who belong to such group will imbibe the peer culture where pre-marital sexual behaviour are encourage that would become the norm. The female adolescents in maintaining social order, seeing his group norm as sacrosanct will align with the group behaviour.

B. Empirical review

Self-Awareness deals with having a clear perception of your personality, including strength, weaknesses, thought, beliefs, motivation and emotions. Self-awareness allows an individual to understand other people, how they perceive you, your attitude and your responses to them in the moment (Warmerdam, 2018). Shelley, Duval and Robert (2015) believed that this happen when an individual focus attention on his/her self, evaluate and compare current behaviour standards and values. This means that he/she has become self – conscious and an objective evaluators of his/her self. In essence, this researchers considered self-awareness as a major mechanism of self-control. Self-awareness is the process of examining our thoughts, feeling and motives (Duval & Robert, 2015) it can lead to having attention focused on ourselves.

The more people get to know themselves, the more probable it is for them to develop independence and self-confidence which paves way for better growth and rational thinking. (Abbasi, Jalilpour, Kamkar, Zadehbaghri & Mohamed, 2011). According to a (Khodayarifard, Shahabi & Zardkhaneh, 2013) stressed that a person's self-awareness enhances his/her acquisition of skills such as decision making; recognizes emotions and masters behaviours through a better knowledge of their needs and characteristics and enables one to be more

realistic when tackling his strong and weak points as well as face life more effectively. Self-awareness causes the self-conscious person to experience fewer problems by consciously managing his/her emotional thoughts and behaviour in proactive way. Self-awareness therefore plays an important role in one behaviour manifestation.

In an empirical study by Eze (2014) carried out on adolescents self-awareness towards premarital sexuality in Awka North and South Local Government Areas of Anambra State. The general purpose of the study was to identify some of the attitudes of adolescents towards premarital sex, the major factors responsible for the attitudes of those adolescents towards premarital sex, and then suggest counseling techniques that will help in controlling the adolescent premarital sex. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study using descriptive survey design. A researchers' developed instrument titled "Adolescent Self-awareness Towards Premarital Sexuality Questionnaire (ASATPSQ)" was the main instrument for data collection, which was validated by experts in Measurement and evaluation. The sample consisted of 102 female students drawn from public secondary schools. The validity ranged from .090 to .091. The statistical analyses used were mean and standard deviation for the research questions and t-test for the hypothesis. The findings of the study revealed that, up to 20% of adolescents in this population have self-awareness (behaviour) towards premarital sex, and the views of the adolescent and adults parents on the adolescents attitude towards premarital sex do differ significantly. The gap inherent in the study was that the sample was too small coupled with the fact that it was majorly concerned with students in public schools without emphasis on their counterparts from private schools. However, the presents study considered a larger sample with due consideration to students in public and private secondary schools.

In a related study Ampuan, Lengkw and Kachima (2012) examined self-awareness and adolescents indulgence in pre-marital sex in South-Africa. Two research questions were formulated to guide the study. The researcher used cross-sectional survey and multi-stage sampling techniques, to select of 105 in-school female adolescents students in public schools for the case study. The instrument used for data collection was a designed questionnaire titled "self-Awareness and Adolescents Indulgence in Pre-Marital Sex Questionnaire (SAAIPMSQ), which was validated by experts and pilot-tested with a reliability index of .76 - .86. The data was analysed with simple regression analysis and the result revealed that self-awareness was one of the factors associated with pre-marital sex. The findings suggested the need for communicating and supporting school students to help them make informed and safer decisions on their sexual behaviour. It was also revealed that self-awareness is very important in the life of anybody and so, in-school adolescence should be trained on how to develop self-awareness for their good. The major weakness of the study was that it was limited to only 102 students. Thus, the sample size was too small for generalization to be effectively made.

In another study, Oladipupo-Okorie (2014) determined the influence of family characteristics and self-awareness on pre-marital sex among secondary school students in Ojo Local Government Area of Lagos State. Four research questions and two hypotheses were answered and tested for the study. The population of the study comprised of 5,000 female adolescence and a sample of 500 female students representing 10% of the target population was used for the study. Simple random sampling was used for the selection of sample. Questionnaire was the main instrument used for data collection, a test-re-test reliability was employed and the index was found to be 0.76 meaning it was reliable. The data collected were analyzed and tested at 0.05 level of significance using Chi-square analysis. The findings revealed that family characteristics, cultural norms and lack of self-awareness were some of the factors responsible for pre-marital sexual behaviour of female students in secondary schools.

The fact that pre-marital sex is a problem emanating from lack of self-awareness and moral issues was also stressed by Patrick (2012) who mentioned that for children to excel in life, there is a great need to recognize that moral character is the vehicle that will carry them through sustainable success in the face of

fame, power and wealth. Furthermore, he emphasized that it is not enough to teach adolescence to act morally, but it is equally important to teach them how to think morally. Hence, it is important to educate, empower and equip our adolescent female students on the practical “whys” for sexual self – awareness and self –control.

Bhandari (2015) conducted a study on Knowledge of Premarital Sex and its Consequences Among Adolescence at a Higher Secondary School in Kenya. Two research questions were answered in the study, using descriptive, cross-sectional study. Simple random sampling method was used for obtaining 141 samples from higher secondary school. Self-administered questionnaire was distributed among adolescents to obtain their responses regarding premarital sex. Out of 141 respondents, the study revealed that 87.2% responded that premarital sex is inappropriate. While 34% responded that the cause of having premarital sex is due to lack of sex education. Regarding the consequences of premarital sex, majority of the respondents were aware different consequences that may occur due to premarital sex. The findings also revealed that majority of the respondents had knowledge about premarital sex and its consequences.

Mahnaz, Fariba, Merghati and Mahgol (2014) study aimed at explaining the actions and functions of families in youths’ awareness of sexual relations. Two research questions and hypothesis were stated in the study. The study employed the descriptive survey design with a sample of Twenty-six single males and females of 18-24 years who were living in Isfahan participated in this qualitative research study. The participants had begun to have some form of sexual activities. Twelve other participants including parents, teachers, school counselors, clinical psychologists, family counselors, and health care providers also took part in the study. Data collection method was based on semi-structured interview and observing the sexual actions and interactions of youths at different levels. In order to analyze the data, the researcher used constant comparison analysis of investigation. The results showed that five main concepts are involved in the formation of sexual relations before marriage, including “parents’ child-rearing practices”, “parents’ interactions”, “children's economic support”, “religious beliefs,” and “sexual awareness”.

Again according to Action Health incorporated in Inayi (2015) who conducted a study on adolescent awareness of age of indulging in premarital sexuality. The result showed that 56% of female adolescents in Nigerian secondary schools who indulge in premarital sex were less than 20 years of age who knew little or nothing about themselves. It was also discovered that over 60% of the adolescents were ignorant of the fact that they can get pregnant when they experimented sex for the first time and that 80% of unsafe abortion complication occurred with adolescents.

Research design

The study utilizes the survey design which is defined by Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim and Ekuri, (2004) as the collection of data to accurately and objectively describe existing phenomena. This is a type of research that studies large and small populations by selecting and studying samples chosen from the population to discover the relative incidence, distribution, interrelations of sociological and psychological variables. Great strength of the survey method, when well carried out, lies in its power to handle large numbers, to reach the situations that other methods cannot reach, and to capitalize on the natural variation between people in the real world (Jambo 2008). According to Jambo (2008) well designed survey can produce a large amount of data, coded for easy analysis, on a large number of people. If the samples are properly drawn, it will allow generalization from the traits of the sample to the probable traits of the population.

Population/Sample

The total sample of the study consisted of 850 In-school female adolescents in senior secondary two (SS2) classes of 2019/2020 academic session from a population of 11, 002.

Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection in this study was named, Self-awareness and In-school Female Adolescent Students Opinion Questionnaire (S-AIFASOQ).

General Description of Research Variables

The study was aimed at investigating the influence of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in secondary schools in Odukpani LGA of Cross River State – Nigeria. The major independent variable of this study was self-awareness. The dependent variable in this study is premarital sexuality categorized on the basis of intimacy, romance and sexual promiscuity and was measured continuously. Results of the descriptive statistics are presented in Table 1 and 2.

Data Analysis

Research questions: How does self-awareness influence pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in terms of intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity.

Table 1 showed the responses on self-awareness of in-school female adolescents in Odukpani Local Government Area. On the issue of whether or not, the female in-school adolescents were intimidated by their friends, 297(35%) strongly agree, 337(40%) agree, 109(13%) disagree while 107(12%) strongly disagree. On item 2, "I like studying hard", 319(38%) strongly agree, 344(40%) agree, 86(10%) disagree while 101 (12%) strongly disagree. On item 3 "I am not easily carried away by gifts" 177(21%) strongly agree, 229(27%) agree, 421(50%) disagree while 23(2%) strongly disagree. On item 4, " I am addicted to watching television" 485(57%) strongly agree, 199 (23%) agree, 87(11%) disagree, while 71(9%) strongly disagree. On item 5, " I like knowing the root of the matter", 308(36%) strongly agree, 242(28%) agree, 142(17%) disagree while 158(19%) strongly disagree. On item 6, "I am weak towards investigating things", 408(48%) strongly agree, 17(2%) agree, 337(40%) disagree while 88(10%) strongly disagree.

TABLE 1: Influence of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in secondary schools

S/N	SELF-AWARENESS	SA%	A%	D%	SD%	Total
1.	I am not easily intimidated by friends.	297(35%)	337(40%)	109(13%)	107(12%)	850(100%)
2.	I like studying hard.	319(38%)	344(40%)	86(10%)	101(12%)	850(100%)
3.	I am not easily carried away by gifts.	177(21%)	229(27%)	421(50%)	23(2%)	850(100%)
4.	I am addicted to watching television	485(57%)	199(23%)	87(11%)	71(9%)	850(100%)
5.	I like knowing the root of the matter.	308(36%)	242(28%)	142(17%)	158(19%)	850(100%)
6.	I am weak towards investigating things.	408(48%)	17(2%)	337(40%)	88(10%)	850(100%)

Table 2 presents pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in terms of intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity.

In terms of intimacy, item 1 " I do not like carrying friends of the opposite sex on my laps", 320(37%) strongly agree, 273(32%) agree, 199(23%) disagree while 92(8%) strongly disagree. On item 2 " I like kissing my boyfriend on the lips", 187(22%) strongly agree, 348(41%) agree, 178(21%) disagree while 137(16%) strongly disagree. On item 3, "I like reading novels and magazine about sexual intercourse" 724(85%) strongly agree with the statement, 33(4%) agree, 11(2%) disagree while 82(9%) strongly disagree. Item 4 " It is not proper to manipulate your sex organs to relieve yourself of sexual urge" 310(36%) strongly agree to the statement, 277(33%) agree, 122(14%) disagree while 141(17%) strongly disagree. On item 5, "Browsing to see naked people on the internet is part of education" 487(57%) strongly agree, 322(38%) agree, 28(3%) disagree while 13(2%) strongly disagree. On item 6, " There is nothing wrong about allowing my friend to touch or rub

various part of my body" 118(14%) of the respondents strongly agree, 87(10%) of the respondents agree, 399(47%) disagree while 176(29%) of the respondents strongly disagree.

In terms of romance, item 7 "touching my breast by opposite sex is fun", 304(36%) strongly agree to the statement, 293(34%) agree, 219(26%) disagree while 34(4%) strongly disagree. Item 8 " I feel excited when I hug embrace and kiss my boyfriend" 455(54%) strongly agree, 217(26%) agree, 98(11%) disagree while 80(9%) strongly disagree. Item 9 "Kissing my boyfriend in the public is not a crime" 587(69%) of the respondents strongly agree to the statement, 172(20%) agree, 59(7%) disagree while 32(4%) strongly disagree. Item 10 "Being embrace by the opposite sex in public does not arouse me" 97(11%) strongly agree, 327(44%) agree, 132(16%) disagree while 294(36%) strongly disagree. Item 11 "Petting below the waist make me feel emotional" 437(51%) of the respondents strongly agree, 388(46%) agree, 15(2%) disagree while 10(1%) strongly disagree. On item 12 "I am easily arouse when I touch he opposite sex" 309(36%) strongly agree, 428(50%) agree to the statement, 57(7%) disagree while 56(7%) strongly disagree.

Table 2: Premarital sexuality among female in-school adolescents

S/N	INTIMACY	SA%	A%	D%	SD%	Total
1.	I do not like carrying friends of the opposite sex on my laps.	320(37%)	273(32%)	199(23%)	58(8%)	850(100%)
2.	I like kissing my boyfriend on the lips.	187(22%)	348(41%)	178(21%)	137(16%)	850(100%)
3.	I like reading novels and magazine about sexual intercourse.	724(85%)	33(4%)	11(2%)	82(9%)	850(100%)
4.	It is not proper to manipulate your sex organs to relieve yourself of sexual urge.	310(36%)	277(33%)	122(14%)	141(17%)	850(100%)
5.	Browsing to see naked people on the internet is part of education.	487(57%)	322(38%)	28(3%)	13(2%)	850(100%)
6.	There is nothing wrong about allowing my friend to touch or rub various part of my body.	118(14%)	87(10%)	399(47%)	176(29%)	850(100%)
	ROMANCE					
7	touching my breast by opposite sex is fun	304(36%)	293(34%)	219(26%)	34(4%)	850(100%)
8.	I feel excited when I hug embrace and kiss my boyfriend	455(54%)	217(26%)	98(11%)	80(9%)	850(100%)
9.	Kissing my boyfriend in the public is not a crime	587(69%)	172(20%)	59(7%)	32(4%)	850(100%)
10.	Being embrace by the opposite sex in public does not arouse me	97(11%)	327(44%)	132(16%)	294(36%)	850(100%)
11.	Petting below the waist make me feel emotional	437(51%)	388(46%)	15(2%)	10(1%)	850(100%)
12.	I am easily arouse when I touch he opposite sex	309(36%)	428(50%)	57(7%)	56(7%)	850(100%)
	SEXUAL PROMISCUITY					
13	I easily accept any man that approaches me	195(23%)	124(15%)	397(46%)	134(16%)	850(100%)
14	I find joy hanging out with several men	138(16%)	479(56%)	218(26%)	15(2%)	850(100%)
15	I am always joyful when I spend my time with the opposite sex	537(63%)	177(21%)	56(7%)	80(9%)	850(100%)
16	I like double dating	198(23%)	231(27%)	133(16%)	288(34%)	850(100%)
17	I dislike being approached by many men	98(12%)	109(13%)	326(38%)	317(37%)	850(100%)
18	Sleeping around make me feel happy	120(14%)	198(23%)	438(52%)	94(11%)	850(100%)

In terms of sexual promiscuity, item 13 "I easily accept any man that approaches me", 195(23%) strongly agree to the statement, 124(15%) agree to the statement, 397(46%) disagree while 134(16%) strongly disagree. For item 14, "I find joy hanging out with several men" 138(16%) strongly agree to the statement, 479(56%) agree, 218(26%) disagree while 15(2%) strongly disagree. For item 15 "I am always joyful when I spend my time with the opposite sex", 537(63%) strongly agree, 177(21%) agree, 56(7%) disagree while 80(9%) strongly disagree. For item 16, "I like double dating" 198(23%) of the respondents strongly agree to the statement, 231(27%) of the respondents agree, 133(16%) disagree while 288(34%) strongly disagree. For item 17, "I dislike being approached by many men, 98(12%) strongly agree, 109(13%) agree, 326(38%) disagree while 317(37%) strongly disagree to the statement. On item 18, "Sleeping around make me feel happy"

120(14%) of the respondents strongly agree to the statement, 198(23%) agree, 438(52%) disagree while 94(11%) strongly disagree to the statement.

Test of Hypothesis

Self-awareness has no significant influence on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in terms of intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity and overall premarital sexuality. The independent variable in this hypothesis is self-awareness categorized into high, moderate and low. The dependent variable is premarital sexuality categorized in terms of intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity and overall premarital sexuality.

Table 3: Summary of One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality (with the following dimensions: intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity and overall)

Sexuality variable	Group	Levels	N	Mean	SD
Intimacy	1	High	309	15.9223	4.82625
	2	Moderate	345	16.3913	3.34550
	3	Low	197	16.8477	3.31773
		Total	850	16.3267	3.95373
Romance	1	High	247	15.6640	5.0947
	2	Moderate	342	16.8246	3.24985
	3	Low	262	16.3015	3.44924
		Total	850	16.3267	3.95373
Sexual Promiscuity	1	High	256	15.6953	5.02396
	2	Moderate	315	16.8984	3.25887
	3	Low	280	16.2607	3.44437
		Total	850	16.3267	3.95373
Overall	1	High	336	16.0030	4.73444
	2	Moderate	380	16.3211	3.28619
	3	Low	135	17.1481	3.41095
		Total	850	16.3267	3.95373

Variables	Sources of variation	Sum of square	Df	Mean of square	F	P – Value
Intimacy	Between group	105.443	2	52.722	3.392	.034
	Within group	13181.741	848	15.545		
	Total	13287.184	850			
Romance	Between group	193.422	2	96.711	6.263	.002
	Within group	13093.762	848	15.441		
	Total	13287.184	850			
Sexual promiscuity	Between group	206.233	2	103.117	6.685	.001
	Within group	13080.951	848	15.426		
	Total	13287.184	850			
Overall	Between group	126.319	2	63.159	4.070	.017
	Within group	13160.866	848	15.520		
	Total	13287.184	850			

*Significant at p<.05, df =2, 848

To answer the descriptive statistics for the three levels of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality with the following dimensions: intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity and overall premarital sexuality, the result as presented in Table 3 indicates that for level of intimacy, high has a mean of 15.92 and standard deviation of 4.83, moderate has a mean of 16.39 and standard deviation of 3.35 and low has a mean of 16.85 and standard deviation of 3.32. For level of romance, high has a mean of 15.66 and standard deviation of 5.10, moderate has a mean of 16.82 and standard deviation of 3.25 and low has a mean of 16.30 and standard deviation of 3.45. For level of sexual promiscuity, high has a mean of 15.69 and standard deviation of 5.02, moderate has a mean of

16.89 and standard deviation of 3.26 and low has a mean of 16.26 and standard deviation of 3.44. For overall level of premarital sexuality, high has a mean of 16.00 and standard deviation of 4.73, moderate has a mean of 16.32 and standard deviation of 3.29 and low has a mean of 17.15 and standard deviation of 3.41. Thus low level of overall premarital sexuality dominated the study.

The statistical tool used to test the hypothesis was One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This is because three dependent groups of high, moderate and low were compared on a dependent variable, and it was tested on each of the three sub-dimension of pre-marital sexuality (intimacy, romance and promiscuity). The results of the analysis are presented in Table 3. The upper part of the table shows the mean and standard deviations for three groups of students on the pre-marital sexuality variables (students with high, moderate and low levels of promiscuity). The low part of the table shows the actual results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA). The table shows that the calculated F – values for level of intimacy is 3.392 level of romance 6.263 level of sexual promiscuity 6.685 and overall of 4.070. The table also shows that the calculated p-values of .034, .002, .001 and .017 are all significant for the sub-components of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality and overall at .05 level with 2 and 848 degree of freedom. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected for all the sub components of pre-marital sexuality. This implies that there is a significant influence of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality in all the components and overall premarital sexuality. In order to clearly understand the pattern of the significant F-ratio, a Post Hoc comparison was executed with Fisher's Least Significance Difference (LSD) to determine which exact groups (High, Moderate and Low) differ significantly with the following dimensions: the various sub-components and over all pre-marital sexuality. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 7.

Level of Intimacy

It can be observed in Table 4 that students with high level of self-awareness in respect to intimacy are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with moderate awareness (mean difference =.47, $p > .05$). Similarly, students with high level of self-awareness in respect to intimacy are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =.93, $p < .05$). The result also showed that students with moderate level of self-awareness in respect to intimacy are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =.46, $p > .05$). However, the difference between students with high self-awareness and students with moderate self-awareness as well as the difference between students with moderate awareness and students with low self-awareness in respect to intimacy was not significance at .05 level of significance while the difference between students with high self-awareness and students with low self-awareness in respect to intimacy was significance at .05 level of significance.

Level of Romance

It can be observed also in Table 4 that students with high level of self-awareness in respect to romance are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with moderate awareness (mean difference =1.16, $p < .05$). Similarly, students with high level of self-awareness in respect to romance are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =.64, $p > .05$). The result also showed that students with moderate level of self-awareness in respect to romance are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =.52, $p > .05$). However, the difference between students with high self-awareness and students with moderate self-awareness in respect to romance was significance at .05 level of significance, while the difference between students with high self-awareness and students with low self-awareness and the difference between students with moderate self-awareness and students with low self-awareness in respect to romance was not significance at .05 level of significance.

Level of sexual promiscuity

It can be observed also in Table 4 that students with high level of self-awareness in respect to sexual promiscuity are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with moderate awareness (mean difference =1.20, $p < .05$). Similarly, students with high level of self-awareness in respect to sexual promiscuity are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =.57, $p > .05$). The result also showed that students with moderate level of self-awareness in respect to sexual promiscuity are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =.64, $p > .05$). However, the difference between students with high self-awareness and students with moderate self-awareness in respect to sexual promiscuity was significance at .05 level of significance. The difference between students with high self-awareness and students with low self-awareness in respect to sexual promiscuity was not significance at .05 level of significance, while the difference between students with moderate self-awareness and students with low self-awareness in respect to sexual promiscuity was significance at .05 level of significance.

Overall effect

The overall result showed that students with high level of self-awareness are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with moderate awareness (mean difference =.32, $p > .05$). Similarly, students with high level of self-awareness are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =1.15, $p < .05$). The result also showed that students with moderate level of self-awareness are less involve in premarital sexuality than students with low awareness (mean difference =.83, $p < .05$). However, the difference between students with high self-awareness and students with moderate self-awareness was not significance at .05 level of significance, while the difference between students with high self-awareness and students with low self-awareness as well as the difference between students with moderate self-awareness and students with low self-awareness was significance at .05 level of significance.

Table 4: Result of Fishers Least Significance Difference (LSD) of the influence of self-awareness on premarital sexuality (with the following dimensions: intimacy, romance, sexual promiscuity and overall)

(I) intimacy	(J) premarital sexuality	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
High	Moderate	.46897	.129
	Low	.92539*	.010
Moderate	High	.46897	.129
	Low	.45641	.195
Low	High	.92539*	.010

I) Romance	(J) premarital sexuality	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
High	Moderate	1.16059*	.000
	Low	.63756	.068
Moderate	High	1.16059*	.000
	Low	.52303	.105
Low	High	.63756	.068
	Moderate	.52303	.105

(I) sexual promiscuity	(J) premarital sexuality	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
High	Moderate	1.20310*	.000
	Low	.56540	.096
Moderate	High	1.20310*	.000
	Low	.63770*	.048
Low	High	.56540	.096
	Moderate	.63770*	.048

Overall	Pre-marital sexuality	Mean Difference (I-J)	P-value
High	Moderate	.31808	.281
	Low	1.14517*	.004
Moderate	High	.31808	.281
	Low	.82710*	.036
Low	High	1.14517*	.004
	Moderate	.82710*	.036

Discussions of finding

The null hypothesis stipulated that self-awareness has no significant influence on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents, with the following dimensions: Intimacy, romance and sexual promiscuity. The result of hypothesis one as presented in Table 3 revealed that, there is significant influence of self-awareness on pre-marital sexuality of in-school female adolescents in secondary schools. The result indicates that students' level of pre-marital sexuality with respect to level of intimacy for those between high and low is significantly higher than for those with high and moderate and with moderate and low.

This therefore implies that students with moderate and low level of self-awareness are more involved in pre-marital sexuality than students with high level of self-awareness. In level of romance, the result indicate that students level of pre-marital sexuality for those between high and moderate is significantly higher than for those with moderate and low. This implies that students with high level of self-awareness are less involved in pre-marital sexuality than students with moderate and low levels of self-awareness. The result as well indicated that with respect to level of sexual promiscuity, students between high and moderate are significantly higher than those with low level of sexuality. This implies that students with high level of self-awareness are less involved in pre-marital sexuality than those with low level of self-awareness.

The result additionally indicates that student's level of pre-marital sexuality with respect to overall pre-marital sexuality for those between high and low, moderate and low is significantly higher than for those between high and moderate. This implies that students with high and moderate levels of self-awareness are less involved in pre-marital sexuality than those with low levels of self-awareness.

One needs to relate the findings to the relevant theories that under girded the study in this case; the theory in question is that of Goleman Emotional intelligence theory. The study posited of significant influence of self-awareness on premarital sexuality of in-school female adolescent in the three dimensions: intimacy,

romance and sexual promiscuity. An adolescent low score in self-awareness, an emotional intelligence variable indicates a low degree of knowledge of self-awareness expressed by in-school female adolescents, this lack of knowledge of self-awareness causes the female adolescents to be distracted from academic work and indulge in pre-marital sexuality. This is because in-school female adolescents lack emotional intelligence which is a vital tool which enables one to be wise, disciplined and focus. Also this is the reason why adolescents who have high and moderate scores in self-awareness less indulges in pre-marital sexuality. Using the words of Goleman (2017) self-awareness is the key corner stone to emotional intelligence; it is the ability to monitor our emotions and thought from moment to moment. It is the key to understanding ourselves better being at peace and proactively managing our thought emotion and behaviour.

This is as well consistent with Deborah and Tolman (2014) who believed that indulgence of female adolescents in premarital sex is as a result of lack of self-awareness and the age, believing that female adolescents aged 15 to 18 years do not fully understand their body mechanism and when they are safe to have sex or not supposed to have sex. The researchers suggested that female adolescent level of emotional intelligence better predicts outcome of adolescent behaviour and choice of action of either to indulge in pre-marital sex or not. It is also similar to the finding of Ampuam, Lengkwon and Kachima (2012) who agreed that lack of self-awareness was a contributing factor to female adolescent indulging in pre-marital sex.

Oladipupo-Okorie, (2014) found out that lack of self-awareness and cultural norms and parenting style contribute to in-school female adolescents indulging in pre-marital sex. According to her as regarding parenting style, when a home is not democratically oriented, that home lack warmth needed by adolescents either female or male, but mostly female. This may lead them to some wholesome anti-social behaviours including inability to control their sexual desire. Therefore, the technique adopted by parents in parenting may have effect on the behaviour of in-school female adolescents.

Abbasi et al (2011) found out that if one lacks self-awareness, the person would not be realistic when tackling weak and strong points in life. This is because self-awareness enables one to be conscious of whatever decision to be taken with ease. Mohammed (2011) found out that for a person to acquire skills such as decision making, recognition of emotions and master behaviour and to have knowledge of their needs and characteristic self-awareness is a vital tool. Patrick (2012) believed that in-school female adolescents are not educated, equipped and empowered with the knowledge of sexual self-awareness, this make them indulge in premarital sex.

Conclusion/Recommendations

Based on the findings in the study, it was concluded that in-school female adolescent students indulging in pre-marital sex have strong link with the extent to which they are emotionally intelligent: being aware of themselves, can regulate themselves, can motivate themselves positively and the extent to which they are empathetic to the opposite sex. Students with low level of self-awareness were more involved in premarital sex than students with high and moderate levels of self-awareness. However, students with high level of self-awareness and those with moderate levels of self-awareness were not different in their involvement in premarital sexuality. Based on this, adolescents should be given full orientation on self-awareness which will assist them to avoid becoming victim of **harmful propaganda** and should also take steps to protect themselves from the flood of sexual images and innuendos that are dispensed through books, magazines, music videos, video games, movies, and the Internet. Moral values should be taught at all levels in schools. Values and sexual behaviour lessons could be inputted into various school curriculums. Sex education should be added into secondary school curriculum. This will help students to be more open in discussing sexual matters and equip them for the future.

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